

The Role of Case Manager and the Implementation in Supporting Patient-Centered Care in PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Hospital

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Abstract: The patient care paradigm was patient-centered care (Patient-Centered Care). Patients and families needed accurate information and Pro-fessional Care Providers (PPA) that worked in an integrated manner in providing services to patients. A serious problem arose from the many interdisciplinary conflicts between service providers and the weak of quality control and cost control for hospitals. Case Manager was an important and comprehensive intervention in order to improve quality, control costs, patient safety, integrated care, continuity of service and patient satisfaction. The role of the Case Manager was very important and very complex as part of implementing patient-focused services, helping to improve inter-professional collaboration and other health care teams. The research objective: the objective was to describe the role of the case manager and the implementation in supporting Patient-Centered Care in the hospital. Method: The quantitative method was applied to the phenomenological approach. The main informant was the Case Manager and service supervisor as much as 30 informants. The data was obtained through deep interview and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) Result and Discussion: The role of Case Manager and the implementation had appropriately supported Patient-Centered Care in PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Hospital with the two appointed Case Manager, doctor, and nurse through the decision letter of board directors. The role of the Case Manager in supporting PCC was coordination, communication, supervision, prevention, and planning of patient care. The role had not been optimally done because it was constrained by multi-role constraints, ethical legal and uneven socialization. Conclusion: The role of Case Manager and the implementation at PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Hospital had supported Patient-Centered Care and the dominant role was the role of communication and the role of coordination.

Keywords: Case Manager, Patient-Centered Care.

I. Introduction

Health service providers always pay attention to quality, safety, and cost. Therefore patient safety is a top priority in all forms of hospital activities. To achieve conditions of service that are effective, efficient and safe for patients, it requires commitment and responsibility of all service delivery personnel in the hospital [1]. At this time, patients are increasingly aware of their rights, the doctor and patient relationship is a whole service with personal interaction, not just the focus of treatment. The current paradigm is Customer Focus, doctors at the hospital work as a team in handling patients [2].

Patients and families need information and hope to consult a doctor at any time. With the change in patient attitudes, the quality of hospital services needs to be improved and patient satisfaction needs to be prioritized [3].

The number of interdisciplinary conflicts in providing services to patients, such as doctors with doctors, doctors with nurses and other officers causes patients sometimes cannot voice their internal problems, so the conflicts often occur at the end of each service or during the service. In the hospital, the lack of quality control and cost control is a serious problem for the hospital. Along with the program, BPJS is spotlighted related to cost control. To improve the quality of hospital services, it is necessary to change the perspective of management and clinician. The service is focused on customers by improving the quality of products, services, and information.

The Case Manager is an important and comprehensive intervention in order to improve the quality and safety of patient care, cost control, patient-centered care (Patient-Centered Care), and integrated patient care, continuity of service, patient compliance and patient satisfaction [4].

The case manager task in the hospital is important as part of the application of patient-centered care (Patient-Centered Care). It plays a role in helping to improve inter professional collaboration. Moreover, the case managers facilitate the fulfillment of patient care needs, including family and companions or caregivers [5].

Case managers play an active role as a liaison between patients and doctors or with other health workers needed in gaining care [4]. The importance of the role of the case manager as described above, then every hospital must have a case manager. It is compatible with the Accreditation Standards of KARS in 2012 where hospital accreditation standards require and encourage the development of case management services and use the term Patient Service Manager [6].

II. Research Method

The research method used was a qualitative phenomenological approach; the data collection was through interview and Focus Group Discussion (FGD). The subject of research was all case managers, nurse managers, nurse supervisors, assistant and the head of accreditation in the hospital. The data analysis was data reduction, data presentation, drawing a conclusion. The research location was at PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Hospital.

III. Result and Discussion

The informant in the research consisted of 30 informants to interview and to conduct FGD. The informants are consisted 5 main informants, 10 informant’s triangulation interview, 15 FGD Informants.

Table 1. the main informants interview characteristics about the role of Case Manager and the implementation in supporting Patient-Centered Care in PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Hospital n=5

No	Characteristics	Information	Frequency (f)	Presentation (%)
1.	Sex	a. Male	3	60
		b. Female	2	40
2.	Age	a. 31 - 35 years old	3	60
		b. 36 - 40 years old	2	40
3.	Education	a. S1	3	60
		b. S2	2	40
4.	Working Duration	a. 5 - 10 years	1	20
		b. 11 - 15 years	4	80
5.	Profession	a. Doctor	3	60
		b. Nurse	2	40

In table 1 known that the majority of the main informants' characteristics in the research was male informants (60%), the age was between 31-35 years old (60%), the highest education was S1 (60%), and the average working duration was 11-15 years (80%).

Qualification

Based on the KARS accreditation standard 2012, it is mentioned that the accreditation standard of the hospital should have had the Patient Service Manager (MPP) in each hospital that generally the person named Case Manager. In operating the task as the patient service manager, the Case Manager should serve or handle the service of the patient about 25 patients to 50 patients. It corresponded with the condition service system and cultural work in every Hospital [7].

3.1.1. The competency enhancement

Based on the FGD process and deep Interview with some informants, it was obtained the information that the Case Manager in hospital should have had a letter of assignment from the direction for the job responsibility. It corresponded with the requirements as a case manager, so the authority in conducting the task was clear. Then whether the case manager competency in conducting the task needed the supporting cases from the competence. One of the competencies

needed was the proofs of following case manager training or other case manager training in order to conduct the role as Case Manager, the roles and the tasks could be comprehended and conducted properly In the book [8] stated that a person could conduct the role properly if reliable competence was obtained through the training and other knowledge enhancement. The statement explained that the necessity of enhancing competency or the skills through training, workshop and internship with the expectance for increasing the skills, knowledge and psychomotor.

3.1.2. Work experience

Several informants in FGD and interview stated that the case manager, besides having competency as a case manager in training and education, the case manager also needed to have work experience in working or internship skills in the hospital that applied case manager properly so the experience and the knowledge could be used and applied in hospital. Other necessary experience needed to be the experience in facing service cases or problems. In KARS' book 2016 entitled "the practical guidance of patient service manager-MPP in Hospital" in chapter IV. Chapter IV discussed the manager qualification. The Case Manager, in that chapter, discussed the doctor or nurse could officiate as a case manager with the set of the qualification requirement. The good implementation in case management was affected by age of case manager above 35 years old and the majority had work experience more than 15 years, so the experience in handling cases in the hospital was raised.

3.1.3. The requirement

The Case Manager in PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Hospital had published the policy which consisted Letter of Decision (SK) Hospital's director as appointed requirement as the case manager in a hospital. As the case manager required SK from the director, it should be followed by another requirement as a permanent employee in the hospital. To fulfill the competence and the knowledge of the case manager, the case manager training and workshops were required.

The case manager, nurse should be previously credential to observe their equal ability in individual nurse practice for competence and the requirement. For the hospital that already applied the nurse career path, it could appoint a nurse that had minimal nurse level clinic III (PK III). The case manager, a professional health officer worked in the hospital, worked collaboratively with provisional giving care (PPA) and ensured the patients properly cared about their condition.

3.2. The steps in task implementation

The existence of the case manager role discussed in standard accreditation in chapter III about patient assessment (AP). In the section of aim and objective, it is stated that the patient may receive various types of action or assessment inside or outside the hospital by several multidiscipline sciences and undergo some work unit at the time of patient care service. Therefore, several information could be captured and the implementation task steps of the case manager in the care service to the patient.

3.2.1. Service coordination

Recently, the fitted role of the case manager was intended to coordinate the patient care, to commit the communicate among PPA team, to supervise the patient service care, to do prevention on care duplication, and jointly to active in planning the care of the patient was not optimally conducted.

The result and supported other data in the medical imprint, hence the formal meeting was necessary to conduct from various care services of professional teams that care and treat the patient with the regular coordination function through the case report and patient round. The role of the case manager mentioned in the coordinating process was as facilitated person or connecting the meeting [9].

3.2.2. Communication

The other role and the task of the case manager were about communication. To facilitate the service in completing the problems was needed communication among PPA members in order to obtain the exact solution to the problem. The function of communication was needed in order to avoid misunderstanding in perception or responding to the problem. The role of the case manager in communication was regarded not optimal according to the informants because of the lack of understanding about case manager, the case manager newly known, and uneven socialization in all units, so the task implementation became less optimal.

The effective communication conducted among health team involved inpatient service was the important requirement

in providing the health service mainly the focused service on the patient [10].

3.2.3. The care planning

The other role and task of the case manager were about the planning. The planning needed in the service given or the deciding problem was not wrong in doing. The planning needed to facilitate service in completing the problems, but based on the deep interview and FGD to several informants, the data obtained showed that the function of planning function was not fully done due to several factors.

3.3. The complete document

The article 29 UU No. 44 of 2009 about the hospital, stated that the hospital required to compose and apply the internal hospital regulation (hospital by law), besides article 13 act 3 stated that every health staff working in hospital should work based on the applied SPO. The regulation or law composed should be completed with policy document and technical instruction which design to facilitate the implementation of WHO 2014 regulation.

The established regulation by the hospital to conduct by case manager including policy document and standard operational procedure had not available in the room or related service unit. The document or the policy about the role of the case manager and the responsible in case managers were required. That stuff we're used to know how the policy of case manager, case manager service, the implementation, and whoever is a case manager. All documents and policies had not been known by the unit especially managing units.

The research of sapkota, Gupta & mainly supported the importance of SPO to the hospital [11]. The result of case manager instrument development in one of the hospitals in Surabaya Dr. Soetomo stated that the existence of a composed case manager instrument could help the case manager in conducting the functions in hospital, so SPO was urgently required to conduct task and activity with preferable service result.

All activities conducted by the case manager had been discharged but the guidance to operate the activity such as policy document, SPO in hardcopy or softcopy had been available and undistributed inpatient and out-patient care unit; restrictedly in the socialization of accreditation. It was compatible with the statement of several informants through deep interview and FGD mentioned that several documents such as policy and SPO were undistributed in-service units or even unknown the existence.

The important of documents such as SPO in ministerial regulation LHK RI No: p56/Menlhk-Setjen/2015 article 10 section 3. The guidance and supervision meant were conducted by advocacy, socialization, technical guidance, education, and capacity building of human resources and monitoring and evaluation. Socialization conducted by the case manager was purposed to show the existence of case manager and case manager activity in order to be discovered by all professional provider service (PPA). It was urgently important to conducted socialization for avoiding the malprocedure and appreciation from every PPA and supporting the care service patient team.

IV. Conclusion

The role of the case manager and the implementation had been suitable in supporting the applying patient-centered care in PKU Mu-hammadiyah Yogyakarta hospital, with the pointing of 2 case managers consisted doctor and nurse through SK determined by direction. The applying case manager role in doing coordination of nursing health had wholly done by the case manager. The case manager role in communication to the health team member procedurally. The implementation of the case manager role doing the supervision and prevention; and the next action of the nurse had been optimal done because the ethical legal issue of the authority of the case manager and not all DPJP openly accepted case manager especially senior doctor. The implementation of the case manager in doing prevention to duplicate health care intervention had not been optimal. The case manager in ensuring the care planning to the patient had been conducted by the case manager. Several things to do in homeward planning to the patient identified the need for advanced, the case manager would coordinate with family and Homecare team. The implementation of Patient-centered (PCC) in PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta showed that Yogyakarta has been built with the proven case manager to be case management.

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